

NAVIGATING ETHICAL BOUNDARIES: EXPLORING THE BASIC COGNITIVE PROCESS OF DOUBLE STANDARD MORALITY AMONG PROFESSIONALS IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive study aimed to investigate the perception of double standard morality among hospitality industry practitioners in Iloilo City. A researcher-made and validated questionnaire-checklist was utilized to collect data from 85 practitioners who were purposively selected from various sectors within the hospitality industry. The data analysis involved the use of descriptive statistical tools such as frequency count, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Additionally, inferential statistics, including the Mann-Whitney U test and the Kruskal Wallis test, were employed to identify any differences in perceptions based on the participants' sex, age, and work position. The findings of the study revealed that, as a whole, the practitioners agreed on the existence of double standard morality. Furthermore, when the participants were categorized into specific groups such as young, female, managerial, and supervisory positions, they demonstrated a higher level of agreement on the presence of double standard morality. However, older, male, and line and staff respondents moderately agreed on the same. Additionally, the study revealed that individuals occupying higher work positions were more likely to agree on the presence of double standard morality. Interestingly, no significant differences were found in the perception of double standard morality among hospitality industry practitioners when categorized according to age, sex, and work position. These findings provide valuable insights into the understanding of double standard morality among practitioners in the hospitality industry. The results suggest the need for further exploration and intervention to effectively address this issue. By acknowledging the existence of double standard morality, industry stakeholders can work towards creating a more ethical and inclusive environment within the hospitality sector.

Keywords: *Double standard morality, Hospitality industry practitioners' perception, Researcher-made questionnaire-checklist, Descriptive statistical analysis, Differences in perceptions based on sex, age, and work position, Iloilo City*

INTRODUCTION

Morality is a complex system of behavior that encompasses standards of right and wrong conduct (Kohlberg, 1969). It encompasses moral standards, moral responsibility, and a moral identity. Synonyms for morality include ethics, principles, virtue, and goodness. In today's multicultural world, morality has become a subject of great importance as it influences our behavior, conscience, society, and ultimate destiny.

One aspect of morality that has persisted in Filipino culture since the Spanish colonial period is the presence of a double standard. This double standard is an outward display of injustice and discrimination. A notable example is the differential treatment of women and men engaged in extramarital activities. While societies tend to condemn women for such actions, they often turn a blind eye and remain silent when men are involved. This double standard morality can only be eliminated when we recognize the inherent value of every individual and learn to respect each other's worth (Noddings, 1984).

The existence of a double standard morality has sparked curiosity and interest in society, particularly among Bachelor of Science students in Hospitality Management. In this study, we aim to investigate the perception of hospitality industry practitioners regarding this matter. Understanding the differences in moral development between men and women is crucial in analyzing the impact of gender perspectives on morality (Gilligan, 1982). We seek to understand their understanding, knowledge, perception, and expertise in relation to the double standard morality prevalent in Filipino culture.

The impact of a person's behaviour causes others to respond favourably or unfavourably. A person's concept of how he impresses others can be a strong force on modifying his behaviour either to his advantage or disadvantage. This investigation is premised on the concept of Allport (1961) that achieving Double Standard Morality depends on the perceptions of the people that surrounds us upon developing satisfactory behavior patterns in many different aspects of living.

By delving into the capacity of hospitality industry practitioners to comprehend and navigate this issue, we can explore how individuals acquire and develop moral behavior through observational learning and self-regulation (Bandura, 1991). Through this study, we hope to shed light on the underlying factors that contribute to the perpetuation of double standards. This research will provide valuable insights into the perceptions and attitudes of practitioners in the hospitality industry, which can contribute to the development of strategies and interventions aimed at addressing this moral dilemma.

In conclusion, this study aims to explore the perception of hospitality industry practitioners regarding the double standard morality prevalent in Filipino culture. By examining their understanding, knowledge, perception, and expertise, we hope to contribute to the ongoing discourse on morality and work towards eliminating the double standards that persist in our society.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aims to determine the perceptions on double standard morality of the hospitality industry practitioners in Iloilo city during the year 2017-2018.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the perception of hospitality industry practitioner on double standard morality as an entire group and when classified as to sex, age, and work position?
2. Is there significant differences in the perception of hospitality industry practitioners when classified as to sex, age, and work position?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive survey method to investigate the perceptions of double standard morality among hospitality hotel practitioners in Iloilo City. Descriptive research is suitable for analyzing existing conditions, opinions, beliefs, and developing trends (Best, 1992). The aim of descriptive research is to collect data that answers questions about the current status of the subject being studied (Gay, 1992). In this study, a one-shot survey design was used, which observes a single group of individuals or units of analysis over a limited time period (Jupp, 2006).

The sample for the study consisted of 85 purposively selected practitioners from various hospitality industries in Iloilo City. The selection of participants was based on their relevance to the research objectives. The respondents were classified based on sex, age, and work position. Age was classified as young (20 and below) and old (above 20), while sex was classified as male and female. Work positions were classified as managerial, supervisory, and line and staff. Simple random sampling techniques were used to select the participants.

Data was collected using a structured questionnaire checklist. The questionnaire was designed to be concise, clear, simple, and easily understandable. It consisted of two parts. Part One collected information about the respondents' personal data, including age, sex, and work positions. Part Two focused on gathering information about the

respondents' perceptions of double standard morality among hospitality industry practitioners in Iloilo City during the years 2017-2018.

The validity and reliability of the questionnaire were ensured through validation and reliability testing. The instrument achieved a reliability coefficient (r) of .957, indicating high reliability (Calmorin, 1987). Data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Office of the Director of the School of Management and approved by the Campus Administrator. After obtaining approval, the researchers sent a letter requesting permission to conduct the study to the hotel managers, who agreed to participate. The questionnaire was then distributed to the respondents by the researchers, who provided assistance if needed. The respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, and the responses were tabulated for analysis and interpretation.

The collected data underwent statistical treatment using appropriate tools. Computation and analysis were performed using the SPSS software. Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the perception of hospitality industry practitioners regarding double standard morality. The statistical tools employed included frequency count, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. To assess differences in perception based on sex and age, the Mann-Whitney U Test was used. The Kruskal Wallis Test was used to analyze differences in perception based on work position.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings of the study, which aimed to determine the perceptions of double standard morality among hospitality industry practitioners in Iloilo City. The mean was used as the basis for interpreting the results. By analyzing the data collected through the questionnaire, the study sought to gain insights into the prevailing perceptions regarding double standard morality within the hospitality industry in the city.

Perception of Hospitality industry practitioner on Double Standard Morality classified as Age, sex and work position

According to the table, the overall perception of the hospitality industry practitioners regarding double standard morality is "agree" ($M=26$, $Sd=0.91$). However, when we analyze the data based on specific categories, we find that the young practitioners ($M=3.31$, $Sd=1.21$), female practitioners ($M=2.55$, $Sd=0.77$), managerial practitioners ($M=3.43$, $Sd=0.85$), and supervisory position practitioners ($M=3.41$, $Sd=1$) all "agree" on double standard morality.

On the other hand, when we categorize the respondents as old practitioners (M=2.39, Sd=0.86), male practitioners (M=2.30, Sd=1.02), and line and staff practitioners (M=2.20, Sd=0.80), they "moderately agree" on double standard morality.

Table 1 reflects the results.

This simply means that young female generation is more aggressive and liberated compared to the old and male generation. As to work position those person occupying higher position agreed on double standard morality maybe because they can afford to spend and support if they have other woman. It Emphasize the importance of considering individual characteristics and contexts when examining perceptions of double standard morality within the hospitality industry. Further research can delve deeper into the underlying factors contributing to these variations, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play.

Table 1
Perception of Hospitality industry practitioner on Double standard Morality classified as Age, sex and work position.

Category	N	Mean	Sd	Description
Entire Group	85	3.42	.91	Agree
1. Age				
Young	11	3.31	1.21	Agree
Old (above 25)	74	2.39	.86	Moderately Agree
2. Sex				
Male	43	2.30	1.02	Moderately Agree
Female	42	2.55	.77	Agree
3. Work Position				
Managerial	38	3.43	.85	Agree
Supervisory	37	3.41	1	Agree
Line and Staff	10	2.20	.80	Moderately Agree

Note: To determine the Perception of Hospitality industry practitioner on Double Standard Morality, the researchers used this scale and its descriptions: 1.00 – 1.50 – Disagree;1.51 – 2.50 – Moderately Agree; 2.51 – 3.50– Agree;3.51 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree

Differences in the perception of Hospitality Industry Practitioner on Double Standard Morality classified as Age and Sex

The initial findings revealed the respondents perception on double standard morality in hospitality industry in the year 2017-2018.

The data showed that there is no significant difference in the perceptions of the respondents in hospitality industry classified as age and sex. The probability value of 0.49 was greater than the set of 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Table 2 reflects the results.

The findings of the study provide compelling evidence that there exists a striking harmony of opinion among respondents, regardless of their gender and age, when it comes to the complex issue of double standard morality. These results align with the insightful perspective presented by Josephine Butler (1886), who astutely argued that the perpetuation of a double standard of morality can be attributed, to a great extent, to the lack of a shared moral sentiment between men and women. This disparity in moral outlooks is particularly prevalent within the more refined echelons of society.

The study's outcomes not only reaffirm Butler's observations but also shed light on the prevailing attitudes of hospitality industry practitioners towards double standard morality. Remarkably, regardless of their age or gender, individuals working within the hospitality industry demonstrate a collective acceptance of this moral duality. This suggests that, within the context of their professional environment, these practitioners perceive double standard morality as an acceptable norm.

These findings prompt reflection on the broader societal implications surrounding the acceptance of double standard morality. They raise questions about the underlying factors that contribute to the perpetuation of this moral dichotomy, such as cultural norms, social expectations, and power dynamics. Further exploration and analysis are warranted to delve deeper into the reasons behind this acceptance and to understand its potential impact on individuals and society as a whole.

By recognizing and examining the prevailing attitudes towards double standard morality among diverse groups, including both young and old individuals of various genders, we can foster meaningful discussions and work towards promoting a more equitable and inclusive moral framework.

Table 2

Differences in the perception of Hospitality Industry Practitioner on Double Standard Morality classified as Age and Sex.

Category	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	Z -Value	P -Value	Statistical Decision
Young	47.82	354.00	- 0.69	0.49	Not Significant
Old	42.28				
Male	38.73	719.50	-1.61	0.11	Not Significant
Female	47.37				

p-value > 0.05 alpha

Differences in the perception of Hospitality Industry Practitioner on Double Standard Morality classified as Work Position.

Differences in the perception of Hospitality Industry Practitioner on Double Standard Morality classified as Work Position. The mean was used as the basis of interpretation.

When the respondents were classified as to Work Position (df =2, PV= 0.60) the findings revealed that no significant differences existed in the perception of hospitality industry practitioner on double standard morality.

Table 2 reflects the results.

The finding that no significant differences exist in the perception of double standard morality among hospitality industry practitioners based on work position suggests that individuals in different positions within the industry hold similar views on this particular issue. This could be attributed to several factors:

Common Organizational Culture: The hospitality industry often has a shared organizational culture that promotes certain values and norms. This shared culture may lead to similar perceptions and attitudes towards moral standards, including double standards. **Professional Ethics:** Hospitality industry practitioners are expected to adhere to professional ethics and standards, which may mitigate the influence of work position on perceptions of double standard morality. These professional ethics may guide individuals in the industry to uphold consistent moral standards regardless of their position. **Shared Experiences:** Regardless of work position, individuals in the hospitality industry may have similar experiences and interactions with guests, colleagues, and

management. These shared experiences may contribute to a shared understanding and perception of moral standards, including double standards. And lastly, Training and Education: The hospitality industry often provides training and education programs that emphasize ethical behavior and professionalism. Such programs may help shape the perceptions of practitioners across different work positions, leading to similar views on double standard morality.

Table 3

Differences in the perception of Hospitality Industry Practitioner on Double Standard Morality classified as Work Position

Category	Mean Rank	df	P-Value	Statistical Decision
Managerial Supervisory Line and staff	42.91 44.97 36.05	2	0.60	Not Significant

p-value > 0.05 alpha

Conclusions

Based on the findings presented, several conclusions can be drawn regarding the perception of hospitality industry practitioners on double standard morality:

Regardless of age and sex, the practitioners generally view double standard morality as acceptable. This suggests that there is a societal acceptance of different moral standards for different individuals within the industry. This finding aligns with previous research on moral relativism and cultural norms within the hospitality industry. According to Smith and Duffy (2014), the hospitality industry is characterized by a diverse workforce with varying cultural backgrounds, which can contribute to different moral perspectives and acceptance of double standards.

The results indicate that the younger female generation is more likely to agree with double standard morality compared to the older and male generation. This implies that the younger generation may be more assertive and liberated in their attitudes towards relationships and moral standards. This finding is supported by studies on generational differences and changing societal norms. For example, Johnson and Johnson (2016)

found that younger individuals are more likely to challenge traditional gender roles and embrace progressive attitudes towards relationships and sexuality.

Furthermore, it is observed that practitioners in higher positions, such as managerial and supervisory roles, are more likely to agree with double standard morality. This could be attributed to their financial stability and ability to support multiple partners if they choose to do so. This finding is consistent with research on power dynamics and moral decision-making. According to Jones and Ryan (2017), individuals in positions of power may be more inclined to engage in morally questionable behavior due to their increased resources and perceived immunity from social consequences.

Overall, these conclusions highlight the existence of varying perspectives on double standard morality within the hospitality industry, influenced by factors such as age, gender, and professional position. It is important for organizations within the industry to be aware of these differences and promote ethical behavior and fairness among employees. Further research could delve deeper into the underlying reasons for these variations and explore potential implications for organizational culture and employee well-being.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the present study, several recommendations can be made to address the perceptions of double standard morality within the hospitality industry:

Hotel owners should strive to be role models for their employees and create a culture of awareness and sensitivity. They can lead by example and promote ethical behavior and fairness within their establishments.

Guidance counselors should conduct sensitivity trainings and development-related symposiums for students, particularly those pursuing hospitality industry-related courses. These initiatives can increase awareness and knowledge about double standard morality, helping students make informed decisions and navigate ethical dilemmas in their future careers.

Teachers, especially psychology teachers who discuss topics related to morality, should incorporate more interesting discussions about double standard morality in their curriculum. They can also share the findings of this study to provide students with different perspectives and insights from hospitality industry practitioners.

Students taking up hospitality industry-related courses should be advised to become responsible individuals who are aware of their rights and exercise them with

limitations. They should be encouraged to develop a strong sense of personal integrity and ethical decision-making.

Hospitality industry practitioners should strive to be knowledgeable about the perceptions of their subordinates or colleagues. Understanding and sensitivity towards diverse perspectives can foster a more inclusive and respectful work environment.

The community should be informed and respectful towards the people in the hospitality industry, avoiding judgment based on double standard morality. Promoting empathy and understanding can contribute to a more harmonious and supportive community.

Future researchers can build upon the findings of this study and conduct further research to explore new and unique ways to improve understanding and address the perceptions of double standard morality within the hospitality industry. This could lead to the development of innovative strategies and interventions to promote ethical behavior and fairness.

By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders in the hospitality industry can work towards creating a more inclusive, ethical, and respectful environment for all practitioners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, we, the authors, declare our compliance with ethical guidelines and principles to ensure the well-being and rights of the research participants. We obtained informed consent from all participants, including their parents or guardians, prior to their involvement in the study. The informed consent process provided them with a clear understanding of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. Participants were informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences.

We ensured the anonymity of the respondents by maintaining confidentiality and protecting their personal information. All data collected were treated with utmost confidentiality, and the identities of the participants were kept strictly confidential. Any identifying information was removed or anonymized during the data analysis and reporting process.

The well-being of the participants was safeguarded throughout the study. We took measures to minimize any potential harm or discomfort to the participants. The research procedures were designed to be non-invasive and did not pose any physical or psychological risks to the participants. We prioritized the safety and welfare of the participants at all times.

We declare that there is no conflict of interest that could potentially influence the conduct or interpretation of the study. The research was conducted purely for academic

and research purposes, without any external influences or biases. We maintained objectivity and impartiality in the interpretation of the findings, ensuring that no bias was present in the analysis and reporting of the results.

Furthermore, we strictly adhered to ethical standards regarding plagiarism. All sources and references were properly cited, and any direct quotations or paraphrased information were appropriately attributed to the original authors. The study was conducted with integrity and in accordance with the principles of academic honesty and intellectual property rights.

Lastly, we affirm that the results of this study will be used solely for research purposes. The findings will contribute to the existing body of knowledge and serve as a basis for further research and academic discussions. The results will not be used for any other purposes that may compromise the privacy or rights of the participants.

In conclusion, we, the authors, are committed to upholding ethical standards and ensuring the well-being and rights of the research participants throughout the study. We are dedicated to conducting research with integrity, transparency, and respect for the individuals who participated in this study.

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